

1 **Original Research article**

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3 **Comprehensive characterization by LC-DAD-MS/MS of the phenolic**
4 **composition of seven *Quercus* leaf teas**

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19 ABSTRACT

20 A complete characterization of the phenolic profile of leaves infusions from seven Mexican
21 *Quercus* species was developed using different LC-DAD-MS/MS methodologies. The main
22 families of phenolic compounds identified and quantified were: hydrolyzable tannins and
23 flavonol glycosides, based on their fragmentation patterns and UV spectra, proanthocyanidins
24 analyzed after acid-catalysis in the presence of phloroglucinol, and phenolic acids evaluated
25 using UPLC-triple quadrupole mass spectrometer (QqQ). White oak species showed the largest
26 amount of total phenols (830-2956 mg/L) with hydrolyzable tannins as the predominant group
27 (60-96%), mainly vescavalonic acid, vescalagin, and castalagin. Red species (total phenolics
28 129-280 mg/L) showed proanthocyanidins as the dominant family consisted of units of catechin,
29 gallo catechin and in less amount epicatechin gallate and epigallocatechin gallate and larger
30 percentages of phenolic acids (10-19%).

31

32 **Keywords:** Food analysis, food composition, *Quercus*, polyphenols, proanthocyanidins,
33 hydrolyzable tannins, phloroglucinolysis, LC-MS/MS.

34 **1. Introduction**

35 In recent years, the interest and consumption of herbal infusions (commonly called teas or
36 tisanes) from a great diversity of edible plants is increasing considerably among the Mexican
37 population. These plant species include the genus *Quercus*, which has its diversification center in
38 Mexico, because of 450 species estimated worldwide, about 135–150 are from this country, and
39 86 are considered endemic (Nixon, 1998; Zavala, 1998). 41 *Quercus* species (22 white and 19
40 red) occur in Durango forest-. For many civilizations, local ethnic groups (Mixtecos,
41 Tepehuanos, Totonacas and Tepehuas) have used *Quercus* species for medicinal and food
42 purposes (Luna-José et al., 2003). The use of these herbal infusions as antioxidant nutraceuticals
43 in traditional medicine is a common practice.

44 Recently, tisanes prepared with the leaves of Mexican *Quercus* species (*Q.resinosa*,
45 *Q.sideroxylla*, *Q.eduardii* and *Q.durifolia*) have been reported to exhibit antioxidant activity
46 (Rocha-Guzmán et al., 2012) as well as cardioprotective (Rivas-Arreola et al., 2010), anti-
47 carcinogenic (Rocha-Guzmán et al., 2009), anti-inflammatory (Moreno-Jiménez et al. 2015),
48 antimicrobial and anti-topoisomerase potential (Sánchez-Burgos et al., 2013). Antioxidant
49 activity and inhibitory activity of key enzymes relevant for hyperglycemia and Alzheimer's
50 disease were also observed in hydromethanolic and aqueous extracts of leaves of other *Quercus*
51 species (Custodio et al., 2015; Haidi et al., 2017; Nugroho et al., 2016).

52 These biological activities are thought to be associated, at least in part, with the presence of
53 phenolic compounds. Polyphenols, as a group of secondary metabolites broadly distributed in
54 plant-derived products, have been shown to be responsible for many health benefits, including
55 cardio-protective, anti-cancer, anti-diabetic, anti-aging and neuroprotective effects (Scalbert et
56 al., 2005). Therefore, the characterization of polyphenols is of most importance to confirm the
57 potential health benefits attributed to *Quercus* teas.

58 From a phytochemical point of view, *Quercus* tree is very interesting because of the presence
59 of different families of polyphenols Different parts of the tree (wood, bark, cork, acorns) have
60 been extensively investigated (Cantos et al., 2003; Castro-Vázquez et al., 2013; Fernandes et al.,
61 2011; Fernández de Simón et al., 2006) due to their important role in the maturation of wines
62 inside oak barrels, in the wood industry and human and animal nutrition (Haidi et al., 2017).

63 . Bark and woods, mainly used in cooperages, were especially rich in ellagitannins
64 (castalagin, vescalagin, grandinin and roburins A-E) and low molecular weight phenolics
65 (Castro-Vázquez et al., 2013; Fernandes et al., 2011; Fernández de Simón et al., 2006). A broad
66 variability in the type and content of bioactive compounds characterise wood and bark extracts
67 obtained from different *Quercus* species (Chatonnet & Dubourdieu, 1998; Glabasnia &
68 Hofmann, 2006; Ricci et al., 2016). Ellagitannins and gallotannins were also detected in acorns,
69 used as a feed source for animals (Cantos et al., 2003). Proanthocyanidins were poorly studied
70 and mainly identified in bark (Rosales-Castro et al. 2012) whereas, in leaves (methanolic
71 extracts), flavonol glycosides and acylated flavonol glycosides were mainly reported (Brossa et
72 al., 2009; Haidi et al. 2017; Karioti et al., 2010; Nugroho et al., 2016).

73 Regarding *Quercus* leaf teas (aqueous extracts), commonly consumed by the local ethnic
74 groups, scarce information is available in the literature. Some studies reported the total
75 polyphenol, flavonoid and proanthocyanidin content using spectrophotometric methods that in
76 most cases lead to overestimated results (Moreno-Jiménez et al., 2015; Sánchez-Burgos et al.,
77 2013; Custodio et al., 2015). Chromatographic methods were also used but mainly focused on
78 the determination of a specific group of phenolic compounds, mainly flavonoids and phenolic
79 acids (Rivas-Arreola et al., 2010; Rocha-Guzmán et al., 2009, 2012). To the best of our
80 knowledge, exhaustive quantitative data on the content of individual phenolic compounds in
81 *Quercus* leaf teas are still lacking.

82 In this context, the aim of this work was to obtain a comprehensive characterization of the
83 phenolic composition of *Quercus* leaf teas applying different LC-MS/MS methodologies. Seven
84 Mexican *Quercus* species, i.e. four white species (*Q. resinosa*, *Q. grisea*, *Q. arizonica* and *Q.*
85 *covallata*) and three red species (*Q. sideroxyla*, *Q. durifolia* and *Q. eduardii*) were analysed and
86 compared.

87

88 **2. Materials and methods**

89 *2.1. Chemicals*

90 Methanol, acetone and formic acid were supplied from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain) and
91 acetonitrile from Romil (Barcelona, Spain). Ascorbic acid was purchased from Acros Organics
92 (Geel, Belgium). Phloroglucinol and standards of (+)-catechin, rutin, gallic acid, ellagic acid,
93 chlorogenic acid, 3,4-dihydroxybenzoic acid, 4-hydroxybenzoic acid, 4-*O*-caffeoylquinic acid,
94 caffeic acid, coumaric acid, ferulic acid, syringic acid, 2,4,6-trihydroxybenzaldehyde, sinapic
95 acid, 4,5,-dicaffeoylquinic acid, salicylic acid, rosmarinic acid and 3,4-dicaffeoylquinic acid
96 were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Stock solutions at a concentration of
97 2000 mg/L for each phenolic compound were first prepared in methanol and then serially diluted
98 to working concentrations also in methanol.

99

100 *2.2. Samples and preparation of teas*

101 Leaves from seven *Quercus* Species, i.e. four white oaks (*Q. resinosa*, *Q. grisea*, *Q.*
102 *arizonica* and *Q. covallata*) and three red oaks (*Q. durifolia*, *Q. eduardii* and *Q. sideroxyla*) were
103 obtained from trees located in El Salto and El Mezquital, 9.2-9.4 km from the Mezquital-Charcos
104 Road in Southern Durango, Mexico. The samples were harvested in November 2010. Leaves
105 were air dried under the shade at room temperature until 3% moisture content was reached, and

106 then powered. Oak *Quercus* leaf teas were prepared by adding 0.5 g of powdered leaves into 50
107 mL of water (1% w/v) and heating up at 80 °C for 10 min. Solutions were left to reach room
108 temperature and vacuum filtered. The teas were freeze-dried with a working temperature of
109 -50°C during 96 h, weighted to calculate extraction yield and stored at -80 °C until used. The
110 extraction yield of lyophilized infusions was between 17.8 and 39.1 % depending on the species.

111

112 2.3. Analysis of hydrolyzable tannin and flavonols using HPLC-DAD-MS/MS (IT)

113 *Quercus* leaf teas were analyzed after dissolving 10 mg of freeze-dried sample in 1 mL of
114 water with 1% formic acid. Analyses were carried out operating on an Agilent 1100 LC system
115 (Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany) equipped with a vacuum degasser, autosampler, a
116 binary pump and two detectors in series: a diode-array detector (DAD) and mass spectrometer.
117 Chromatographic separations were performed on a reversed-phase column LiChroCART C-18
118 column (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) (250 x 4.6 mm, particle size 5 µm) at 25°C, using
119 water/formic acid (99:1 v/v) (A) and acetonitrile (B) as mobile phases at 1 mL/min and sample
120 volumes of 10 µL. A solvent gradient was used starting with 2% B to reach 32% B at 30 min,
121 55% B at 48 min, 95% B at 53 min, two minutes at this percentage and again 2% B at 57 min.
122 This last value was maintained for 8 min. Chromatograms were recorded at 280, 320, 360, and
123 520 nm. The mass detector was an ion-trap mass spectrometer (model Esquire 1100, Bruker
124 Daltonik GmbH, Bremen, Germany) equipped with an electrospray ionization system (ESI).
125 Mass scan (MS) and MS/MS data were acquired in negative ionization mode and in the mass
126 range of m/z 100-1500 with target mass 700. Negative ionization mode was found to be more
127 sensitive than positive ionization mode for the determination of phenolic compounds. The
128 capillary voltage was set at 4 kV, and nitrogen was used as drying gas (11 L/min and 350 °C) and

129 nebulizer gas (65 psi). Maximum accumulation time of ion trap and the number of MS
130 repetitions to obtain the MS average spectra were set at 200 ms and 3, respectively. Compound
131 stability was set at 50%. AutoMS(n) mode was used for the MS/MS analysis with three
132 precursor ions and 1V of fragmentation amplitude.

133 The identification of the compounds was achieved by the molecular ion mass, MS/MS
134 fragmentation pattern, UV-Vis spectra, elution order in the HPLC chromatograms, and,
135 whenever possible, chromatographic comparison with authentic standards.

136 Quantification was done in UV using external calibration curve established with gallic acid
137 at 280 nm for the quantification of hydrolyzable tannins, ellagic acid at 360 nm for ellagic acid
138 and its derivatives and rutin at 360 nm for the quantification of flavonols. Compound
139 concentrations were calculated in triplicate and the mean value calculated in each case.

140

141 *2.4. Analysis of proanthocyanidins using phloroglucinolysis reaction*

142 Proanthocyanidins were quantified after acid-catalysis in the presence of phloroglucinol as
143 previously reported by Kennedy & Jones (2001). Briefly, 0.8 mL of the reaction mixture (50 g/L
144 of phloroglucinol and 10 g/L of ascorbic acid in methanol 0.1 N hydrochloric acid) were added
145 to 50 mg of lyophilized sample. The mixture was stirred in vortex and incubated for 20 min at 50
146 °C. The reaction was stopped by placing on ice the samples and dispensing 2 mL of 40 mM
147 sodium acetate. The samples were centrifuged at -3650 x g for 10 min and filtered with PVDF
148 filter 0.22 µm before being injected in HPLC-MS. The same HPLC-DAD-MS/MS instrument
149 described in section 2.3 was used for the analysis of the samples.

150 Chromatographic separations were performed on a reversed-phase column Atlantis C18
151 (250 x 4.6 mm, particle size 5µm) at 25°C, using water/acetic acid (97.5:2.5 v/v) (A) and

152 acetonitrile (B) as mobile phases at 1 mL/min, and volume samples of 20 μ L. Gradient was
153 applied, starting with 3% B , raising to 9% B at 5 min, 16% at 15 min, 50% B at 45 min,
154 returning to the initial conditions (3% B) at 52 min and maintaining these conditions until 57
155 min. Chromatograms were recorded at 280 nm. Mass detector operated in negative ion mode in
156 the range of m/z 100-800 and with a target mass of 300. Nebulizer pressure was set at 65 psi, dry
157 gas flow 11 L/min and dry gas temperature at 325 $^{\circ}$ C. The reaction products obtained after the
158 phloroglucinolysis, flavan-3-ol monomers and phloroglucinol adducts, were identified by their
159 elution order, their UV spectrum and their MS pattern. Quantification was done at 280 nm with
160 the calibration curve of (+)-catechin. The response in UV for the different flavan-3-ols was
161 corrected by the response factors described previously by Kennedy & Jones (2001). The mean
162 degree of polymerization was calculated dividing the sum of all subunits (flavan-3-ol monomers
163 and phloroglucinol adducts, in moles) by the sum of all flavan-3-ol monomers (in moles).

164

165 *2.5 Analysis of low molecular weight phenols using UPLC-ESI-QqQ*

166 Analysis of low molecular weight phenolic compounds was carried out with an Acquity
167 UPLC system (Water Corp., Milford, MA, USA) coupled with a tandem Xevo TQ-S triple
168 quadrupole mass spectrometer (Waters Corp). Phenolic acids were determined with an Acquity
169 UPLC BEH C8 column (100 mm x 2.1 mm x 1.7 μ m) (Waters Corp) operated at 30 $^{\circ}$ C
170 according to Gruz et al. (2008). The elution profile included two solvents, acidified water with
171 7.5 mM formic acid (A) and acetonitrile (B): initial 95% A; 0-0.8 min, 95%; 0.8–1.2 min, 90%
172 A; 1.2–1.9min, 90% A; 1.9–2.4 min, 85% A; 2.4–3.7 min 85% A, 3.7–4.0 min 79% A; 4.0–5.2
173 min, 79% A; 5.2–5.7 min, 73% A; 5.7–8.0 min, 50% A; 8.0–9.0 min, 0% A; 9.0-11.5 min, 95%
174 A; then the column was stabilized for 2 minutes. Data were collected in a multiple reaction

175 monitoring mode (MRM). Negative ionization was used for MS assays. ESI conditions were as
176 follows: capillary voltage 1.56 kV; desolvation temperature 350 °C; source temperature, 150 °C;
177 desolvation and cone gas, 650 L/h and 150 L/h, respectively, and collision gas, 0.14 mL/min.
178 MRM transitions were determined from the MS/MS spectra of the existing phenolic acid
179 standards (**Table S1**) and the results were in accordance to those found in the literature (Gruz et
180 al., 2008). Rutin (20 µg/mL) was used to monitor the stability of the ionization efficiency of the
181 mass spectrometer, and a mixture of different phenolic acids (20 µg/mL) was used to monitor
182 retention time and m/z values. Data acquisition and processing were performed using MassLinx
183 (Waters Corp.) software. Peak identification was based on a comparison of their retention time
184 and MRM transitions with those of pure standards. Quantitative determinations of phenolic acids
185 were carried out using standard calibration curves of the available standards. Validation
186 parameters are summarized in the **Supplementary material, Table S1**.

187

188 2.6 Statistical analysis

189 All samples were analyzed in triplicate. All data are expressed as mean value \pm SD or
190 information about RSD is provided. Graphs of the experimental data were produced using Sigma
191 Plot 12.5 (Systat Software, San Jose, CA, USA).

192

193 3. Results and discussion

194 3.1. Hydrolyzable tannins and flavonols content

195 Phytochemical analysis of oak leaf teas by HPLC-DAD-MS/MS (IT) showed the presence of
196 two families of phenolic compounds identified at 280 (hydrolyzable tannins) and 360 nm

197 (flavonols) (**Fig. 1**). The compounds identified as well as their retention time, [M-H]⁻ ion and
198 MS/MS data are summarized in **Table 1**.

199 Eleven hydrolyzable tannins were identified: two compounds were galloyl esters of glucose
200 (gallotannins) (**7,11**) and seven were combination of galloyl and/or hexahydroxydiphenoyl esters
201 of glucose (ellagitannins) (**3,6,9**) of which four were acyclic C-glycosidic ellagitannins
202 (**1,2,4,10**). Free ellagic acid was also found (**12**).

203 Their fragmentation patterns were in accordance to those found in literature for the same and
204 similar compounds (Araujo et al. 2015; Cantos et al., 2003; Fernandes et al., 2011). The losses of
205 152 mass units indicated the presence of galloyl groups whereas the losses of 302 and the
206 appearance of an ion at *m/z* 301 were indicative of the presence of hexahydroxydiphenoyl groups
207 (HHDp). The fragmentation patterns of two unknown compounds (**5,8**) suggested that they could
208 be hydrolyzable tannins but their structures remain to be elucidated. In particular, according to
209 Salminen et al. (2004), the compound with the molecular mass 1084 g/mol (**8**) could result from
210 the lactonization (loss of water) of the valoneoyl group of castavalonic acid.

211 Some of these hydrolyzable tannins and other with related structures have been widely
212 described in woody samples (Fernandes et al., 2011). In particular, vescalagin and castalagin are
213 hydrolyzable tannins typically found in oak wood and bark (Castro-Vázquez et al., 2013;
214 Fernández de Simón et al., 2006; Prida et al., 2006). Less information is available regarding
215 hydrolyzable tannins in leaves and their infusions. Castalagin, vescalagin and castavalonic acid
216 together with pedunculagin and casuarictin were isolated from aqueous acetone extracts of *Q.*
217 *suber* and *Q. robur* leaves (Ito et al., 2002; Salminen et al., 2004).

218 The concentrations of the major hydrolyzable tannins were evaluated from the HPLC profiles
219 (**Table 2**). It should be emphasized that these values are indicative as they are calculated using
220 external calibration with a limited number of standards. A great variability was observed in the

221 hydrolyzable tannin content of oak species. White species (*Q. grisea*, *Q. resinosa*, *Q. arizonica*,
222 and *Q. convallata*) showed the highest diversity and total amount of hydrolyzable tannins (494--
223 2,844 mg/L) compared to red species (*Q. durifolia*, *Q. eduardii* and *Q. sideroxylla*) (63.9-
224 139mg/L). Values in white species were in accordance to those found in the literature for acetone
225 extracts of *Q. robur* leaves (total hydrolyzable tannins 180 mg/g equivalent to 1,800 mg/L)
226 (Salminen et al., 2004). Acyclic monomeric ellagitannins (vescalagin, castalagin and
227 vescavalonic acid) were the most present ellagitannins in white species, as in the case of *Q.*
228 *robur* leaf extracts (Salminen et al., 2004), being *Q. grisea* the richest species.

229 In addition to hydrolyzable tannins, a number of flavonols were also identified by their UV
230 spectra and fragmentation patterns (**Table 1, Fig. 1**). Glycosides and acylated (malonyl, acetyl,
231 coumaroyl and galloyl) glycosides of the flavonols quercetin (*m/z* 301), isorhamnetin (*m/z* 315)
232 and kaempferol (*m/z* 285) were detected. Their elution orders were in accordance to those
233 described by Karioti et al. (2010) and their fragmentation patterns have been previously reported
234 (Vallejo et al., 2004). Besides, characteristic UV spectra were observed for this family of
235 compounds (**Fig. 2**). For instance, kaempferol hexoside (**19**) and kaempferol-acetyl-hexoside
236 (**24**) (probably glucosides) showed UV spectra characteristic of this flavonol, and the retention
237 time allowed the differentiation of the acetylated derivatives that eluted later than the non-
238 acetylated glycosides. The kaempferol hexosides acylated with one *p*-coumaroyl residue (**26,28**)
239 showed a clear maximum at 315 nm (the wavelength maximum for *p*-coumaric acid) with a
240 shoulder at around 350 nm that reflects the maximum of Band I of the flavonol 3-hexoside.

241 Flavonol glycosides and their acylated derivatives have been previously studied in
242 hydromethanolic and aqueous extracts of leaves from different *Quercus* species (Haidi et al.,
243 2017; Karioti et al., 2010, 2011; Nugroho et al., 2016) but quantitative results for most of the
244 compounds are missing. Some studies have shown that acylated flavonoid glycosides possess

245 dramatically increased antioxidant and antibacterial effects compared to their corresponding
246 glycosides (Mellou et al., 2005) which highlights the importance to find matrixes with high
247 content in acylated flavonols.

248 In this regard, it is interesting to emphasize that a group of polyacylated flavonol glycosides
249 identified in acetone-water extracts of the original leaves were not detected when the teas were
250 prepared (**Figure S1**). These compounds included: kaempferol-di-*p*-coumaroyl hexoside (*m/z*
251 739) (**29**), kaempferol-acetyl-di-*p*-coumaroyl hexoside (*m/z* 781) (**30**) and kaempferol-diacetyl-
252 di-*p*-coumaroyl hexoside (*m/z* 823) (**31**). These compounds were not extracted with water and
253 appeared in the plant residue (paste) obtained after filtration of the tea (**Figure S1**). The low
254 solubility in water of the polyacylated flavonol glycosides was previously observed in aqueous
255 extracts of *Quercus ilex* leaves (Haidi et al., 2017). The presence of different peaks for each
256 compound corresponded to a series of *cis* and *trans* isomers of acylated kaempferol glucosides
257 already identified in methanolic extracts of *Q. ilex* leaves (Haidi et al., 2017; Karioti et al.,
258 2010). Their UV spectra allowed a fast and clear differentiation of the degree of acylation with
259 *p*-coumaric acid (**Fig. 2**). The di-*p*-coumaroyl derivatives showed a maximum at 315 nm that in
260 this case was even higher than in the mono-acylated derivatives, and the shoulder at 350 nm was
261 converted in just an inflection in the spectrum. The maximum for the Band II (268 nm) of these
262 di-*p*-coumaroyl derivatives was also less intense, showing that the two *p*-coumaroyl residues are
263 the main determinants of the UV spectrum. Again, the addition of one or two acetyls to the
264 original di-*p*-coumaroyl glucosides increased the retention time and allowed the differentiation
265 of the degree of acylation.

266 As in the case of hydrolyzable tannins, white *Quercus* species were richer in flavonols (16.5-
267 57.3 mg/L) compared to red species (9.40-25.0mg/L) that showed poorer profiles with some
268 compounds missing. The concentrations were lower to those found in the literature for total

269 flavonol glycosides content of *Q. suber* leaves (around 180 mg/L) (Salminen et al., 2004).
270 However, for some individual compounds (quercetin hexoside, rutin, kaempferol-*p*-coumaroyl
271 hexoside, kaempferol hexoside, kaempferol-galloyl hexoside) the amounts were in the range of
272 previous reports (Haidi et al., 2017; Nugroho et al., 2016). High variability was observed in the
273 content of individual compounds among the different samples, in line with that described in
274 other species (Nugroho et al., 2016).

275

276 3.2. Proanthocyanidin content

277 The products formed after acid-catalyzed cleavage of proanthocyanidins from leaf teas were:
278 galocatechin (monomer (**2'**) (m/z 305) and adduct (**1'**) (m/z 429), catechin (monomer (**5'**) (m/z
279 289) and adduct (**3'**) (m/z 413), epigallocatechin gallate, (monomer (**7'**) (m/z 457) and adduct (**4'**)
280 (m/z 581) and epicatechin gallate (monomer (**8'**) (m/z 441) and adduct (**6'**) (m/z 565) (**Fig. 3**).
281 Regarding proanthocyanidins, this matrix results very interesting because of the presence of
282 different flavan-3-ols. Similar monomeric flavan-3-ol units have been widely described in green
283 tea associated with their preventive effects against cancer, cardiovascular disease and
284 neurological disorders (Zaveri, 2006).

285 Scarce information is available in the literature about proanthocyanidins in *Quercus* species.
286 They have been described in bark (Rosales-Castro et al., 2012) and heartwood (Vivas et al.,
287 2006), in most cases using spectrophotometric analysis with little information about
288 composition. Results found in the literature about leaves and their infusions are focused on the
289 determination of free flavan-3-ols, i.e. catechin, epicatechin, epigallocatechin gallate and
290 epicatechin gallate (Haidi et al., 2017; Nugroho et al., 2016; Rocha-Guzmán et al., 2012) and
291 some dimers such as procyanidin B1, B3 and prodelfphinidin (Brossa et al., 2009; Karioti et al.,
292 2011), but a complete characterization of the proanthocyanidin profile has not been reported so

293 far. Only global evaluations of tannins in leaf teas were carried out using classical chemical
294 methods (Moreno-Jiménez et al., 2015; Sánchez-Burgos et al., 2013).

295 In the present study, phloroglucinolysis has been applied for the characterization of the
296 proanthocyanidin profile of *Quercus* samples for the first time. A large amount of total
297 proanthocyanidins was observed in white species (291-347- mg/L) compared with red species
298 (25.3-163- mg/L) except the variety *Q. grisea* (36.5 mg/L) (**Table 3**). Similar results were found
299 in the literature when total proanthocyanidin content was determined using vanillin-HCL assay
300 in white species (61.2-210.4 mg/L) (Sánchez-Burgos et al., 2013), and red species (73.2-334.0
301 mg/L) (Moreno-Jiménez et al., 2015). Values in the same range (108 mg/L) were also measured
302 in leaf acetone extracts with the butanol-HCl assay (Salminen et al., 2004). It was difficult to
303 compare with the results found in literature, due to the lack of detailed quantitative information
304 on the proanthocyanidin profiles and the different methodologies used.

305 In all species, the predominant flavan-3-ols were catechin and gallo catechin, in contrast to green
306 tea samples where epigallocatechin and epigallocatechin gallate are the preferential compounds
307 (Vivas et al., 2006). Epigallocatechin gallate subunits were not detected in *Quercus* red species.
308 Catechin was present in the same proportion as terminal (monomer) and extension
309 (phloroglucinol adducts) units whereas gallo catechin was in general most present as extension
310 unit, except for *Q. durifolia* where only terminal units were present. The mean degree of
311 polymerization was similar for all species with values between 1.25 for *Q. durifolia* to 3.92 for
312 *Q. grisea*.

313

314 3.3. Phenolic acid content

315 Validation parameters for quantifying phenolic acids in *Quercus* samples by UPLC-ESI-
316 QqQ were established (**Table S1**).

317 From all phenolic acids, nine compounds were identified and quantified in the leaf teas: gallic
318 acid, 3,4-dihydroxybenzoic acid, chlorogenic acid, 4-hydroxybenzoic acid, 4-*O*-caffeoylquinic
319 acid, caffeic acid, coumaric acid, ferulic acid and salicylic acid (**Table 4**). Some of these
320 compounds were previously identified in infusions of similar species (Rocha-Guzmán et al.,
321 2009, 2012). In general higher amounts of total phenolic acids were observed in red species
322 (23.4-41.6 mg/L) compared to white species (8.88-18.6 mg/L). When exploring the profile of
323 phenolic acids present in infusions, gallic acid was the main compound in white species
324 (between 8.63 and 12.8 mg/L) while chlorogenic acid was most present in the red oak species *Q.*
325 *sideroxyla* (21.5 mg/L) and *Q. durifolia* (33.1 mg/L). Caffeic acid, coumaric acid, and ferulic
326 acid were missing in red species and were present at a low amount in the white species (0.01-
327 3.26 mg/L). Results found in the literature with other *Quercus* species were focused on the gallic
328 acid as the main phenolic acid detected. High variability was observed in the amounts quantified
329 for this compound: 0.5 mg/L in acetonic extract of *Q. robur* leaves (Salminen et al., 2004), 14-16
330 mg/L in aqueous extract of *Q. ilex* leaves (Haidi et al., 2017), and 18-188 mg/L in methanolic
331 extracts of Korean *Quercus* leaves (Nugroho et al., 2016).

332

333 3.4. Total phenolic content

334 Total phenolic content for leaf teas, calculated by pooling the HPLC results on individual
335 compounds, ranged from 830 to 2,956 mg/L in white oaks and from 129 to 280 mg/L in red
336 oaks. Results were closely similar to those previously reported with Folin-Ciocalteu methods:
337 1,207 mg/L for *Q. resinosa* and between 209-369 mg/L and 154-314 mg/L for red species
338 (Rocha-Guzmán et al., 2012; Moreno-Jiménez et al. 2015). **Fig. 4** summarizes total phenolic
339 content quantified in the samples and percentages of each class of compounds. The phenolic
340 contents of white species were dominated by hydrolyzable tannins (60-96%), especially in the

341 variety *Q. grisea* where they represented the highest contribution to the total phenol content
342 (96%), followed by proanthocyanidins (1-37 %). The opposite pattern was observed for red oaks
343 (*Q. sideroxyla* and *Q. eduardii*) where proanthocyanidins were the most important constituents
344 representing 55 and 58 %, respectively, followed by hydrolyzable tannins. Besides, red oak was
345 characterized by a higher percentage of phenolic acids (10-19%) compared to white oak (0.6-
346 1%). These differences in the phenolic profiles (total amount and percentage of each family of
347 compounds) could have important influence in the bioactivity of the infusions. Previous studies
348 with similar *Quercus* species showed differences in the antioxidant/antiradical activity of their
349 leaf teas, mainly related to the content of phenolic compounds (Rivas-Arreola et al., 2010;
350 Rocha-Guzmán et al., 2009, 2012; Sánchez-Burgos et al., 2013; Moreno-Jiménez et al., 2015).
351 Besides, considering that herbal teas are complex in composition, the contribution of other
352 phytochemical compounds cannot be ruled out.

353

354 **4. Conclusions**

355 The phytochemical analysis of *Quercus* leaf teas, consumed by different ethnic communities in
356 Mexico, showed the presence of a wide variety of phenolic compounds, plant secondary
357 metabolites that possess various biological activities. Hydrolyzable tannins, flavonol glycosides,
358 proanthocyanidins and phenolic acids were identified and quantified applying different LC-
359 MS/MS methodologies in white and red *Quercus* species. To the best of our knowledge, our
360 study provides the most complete description of the phenolic content of oak leaf infusions
361 conducted so far. Results showed that all species are an important source of valuable phenolic
362 compounds, although variability in the phenolic content was found. These compositional
363 differences could influence in the bioactivity of *Quercus* leaf teas. Further studies would be

364 needed to confirm the implication of these families of polyphenols and to established an
365 expected structure-bioactivity relationship.

366

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374

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505 **Figure Captions**

506 **Fig. 1.** HPLC-UV chromatograms of *Quercus grisea* leaf tea recorded at 280 nm (hydrolyzable
507 tannins) (A) and 360 nm (flavonols) (B). Numbers correspond to the compounds listed in Table
508 1.

509

510 **Fig. 2.** Typical UV spectrum of different acylated glycosides of kaempferol. Numbers
511 correspond to the compounds listed in Table 1.

512

513 **Fig. 3.** HPLC-UV chromatogram of proanthocyanidin cleavage products from *Quercus arizonica*
514 leaf tea following acid-catalysis in the presence of phloroglucinol. *ascorbic acid;
515 **phloroglucinol. Compounds: **1'**, (*epi*)-gallocatechin phloroglucinol adduct; **2'**, gallocatechin;
516 **3'**, (*epi*)-catechin phloroglucinol adduct; **4'**, (*epi*)-gallocatechin gallate phloroglucinol adduct; **5'**,
517 catechin; **6'**, (*epi*)-catechin gallate phloroglucinol adduct; **7'**, epigallocatechin gallate; **8'**,
518 epicatechin gallate.

519

520 **Fig.4.** Contribution of each family of compounds to the total phenolic content in different
521 *Quercus* leaf teas. At the end of each bar percentages of each family (%) are indicated:
522 hydrolyzable tannins/flavonols /proanthocyanidins/phenolic acids.

Table 1. Compounds identified in leaves infusion of different *Quercus* species.

Compound	Retention time (min)	[M-H] ⁻ m/z	MS/MS fragments	Suggested compounds
Tannins				
1	6.08	1101	1083, 1039, 995, 915, 569	Vescavalonic acid
2	7.19	933	915, 871, 569	Vescalagin
3	8.12/10.66	783	481, 301, 244	Di-HHDP hexoside (pedunculagin)
4	8.90/14.13	933	915, 631, 569, 301	Castalagin
5	9.50/11.51	1057	1039, 933, 631, 569	Unknown tannin
6	11.97/14.79	785	783, 633, 615, 483, 301	Digalloyl-HHDP-hexoside
7	16.34/18.11	635	483, 465, 313	Trigalloyl hexoside
8	17.52/19.42	1083	1065, 1021, 631, 569, 452	Unknown tannin
9	18.00	935	783, 633, 463, 301	Galloyl-bisHHDP hexoside (casuarictin)
10	18.45	631	479, 317, 301	Vescalin/Castalin
11	20.01	787	635, 617, 465, 313	Tetragalloyl hexoside
12	22.28	301	271, 257, 229, 185	Ellagic acid
Flavonols				
13	20.95/21.26	615	463, 301, 245, 179	Quercetin-galloyl-hexoside
14	21.96	609	301, 179	Rutin (quercetin-rhamnoside-hexoside)
15	22.63	463	301, 255, 179, 151	Quercetin hexoside
16	24.08	599	447, 313, 285, 169	Kaempferol-galloyl-hexoside
17	24.16	593	285	Kaempferol-rhamnoside-hexoside
18	24.77	623	315, 301, 271, 211	Isorhamnetin-rhamnoside-hexoside
19	24.92	447	285	Kaempferol hexoside
20	25.55	477	357, 315, 301, 271, 257	Isorhamnetin hexoside
21	26.50	533	489, 285	Kaempferol-malonyl-hexoside
22	27.55	505	463, 445, 301, 179	Quercetin-acetyl-hexoside
23	28.32	609	463, 301	Quercetin-coumaroyl-hexoside
24	29.36	489	429, 285	Kaempferol-acetyl-hexoside
25	30.87	519	459, 315	Isorhamnetin-acetyl-hexoside
26	32.01/32.58	593	447, 285	Kaempferol-coumaroyl-hexoside
27	32.82	623	477, 315, 301, 271	Isorhamnetin-coumaroyl-hexoside
28	36.45/37.02	635	575, 489, 327, 285	Kaempferol-acetyl-coumaroyl-hexoside

HHDP: hexahydroxydiphenyl

Table 2. Quantification in HPLC-UV (expressed as mg/L) of *Quercus* leaves infusions prepared dissolving 0.5 g of leaves in 50 mL of hot water.

		<i>grisea</i>	<i>resinosa</i>	<i>arizonica</i>	<i>convallata</i>	<i>durifolia</i>	<i>eduardii</i>	<i>sideroxylla</i>
Hydrolyzable Tannins								
1	Vescavalonic acid	940	343	210	102	93.8	-	-
2	Vescalagin	859	615	116	172	-	-	-
3	Di-HHDP hexoside	160	106	43.9	58.3	-	-	18.9
4	Castalagin	512	318	138	85.8	-	-	-
5	Unknown tannin	70.1	52.7	20.1	20.0	-	-	-
6	Digalloyl-HHDP-hexoside	30.6	8.27	17.1	0.47	32.5	13.5	35.7
7	Trigalloyl hexoside	6.80	3.46	2.10	-	-	-	1.46
8	Unknown tannin	221	78.9	35.8	36.8	-	-	-
9	Galloyl-bisHHDP hexoside	17.4	8.02	3.79	-	-	-	-
10	Vescalin/Castalin	6.27	-	3.11	6.88	-	4.31	-
11	Tetragalloyl hexoside	7.73	-	14.8	-	-	-	-
12	Ellagic acid	12.5	21.3	5.71	12.2	12.3	7.81	7.81
	Total hydrolyzable tannins	2844-	1554-	611-	494-	139-	25.7	63.9
Flavonols								
13	Quercetin-galloyl-hex	1.88	-	3.31	2.53	-	1.25	5.66
14	Rutin	0.81	6.17	2.39	-	4.99	0.20	6.91
15	Quercetin hexoside	2.74	5.41	4.50	2.53	2.53	1.76	3.44
16+	Kaempferol-galloyl-hex +	5.44	4.22	4.57	2.05	1.34	0.28	3.03
17	Kaempferol-rham-hex							
18+	Isorhamnetin-rham-hex +	12.3	2.67	7.16	2.16	1.02	1.83	1.62
19	Kaempferol hexoside							
20	Isorhamnetin hexoside	9.35	-	8.84	3.60	-	0.75	-
21	Kaempferol-malonyl-hex	1.75	0.87	-	0.61	-	-	0.42
22	Quercetin-acetyl-hex	0.58	-	-	-	-	-	-
23	Quercetin-coumaroyl-hex	0.41	0.41	0.45	0.39	0.39	0.29	0.42
24	Kaempferol-acetyl-hex	2.42	1.69	2.05	0.91	-	-	-
25	Isorhamnetin-acetyl-hex	0.55	-	-	-	-	-	-
26	Kaempferol-coumaroyl-hex	14.0	4.69	10.98	0.54	3.69	0.26	1.95
27	Isorhamnetin-coumaroyl-hex	3.74	4.38	4.44	0.40	-	2.30	1.13
28	Kaempferol-acetyl-coumaroyl hex	1.38	1.68	0.80	0.80	-	0.47	0.41
	Total flavonols	57.3	32.2	39.5	16.5	14.0	9.40	25.0

Numbers correspond to compounds identified in Table 1

Hex: hexoside; rham: rhamnoside

Results are mean of three replicates (n=3) and in all cases RSD was below 10%.

Table 3. Procyanidin content (expressed in mg/L), proportions of constitutive flavan-3-ols (extension and terminal units) and mean degree of polymerization (mDP) of leaves infusions from different *Quercus* species calculated after acid catalysis in the presence of phloroglucinol

Procyanidins	<i>grisea</i>	<i>resinosa</i>	<i>arizonica</i>	<i>convallata</i>	<i>durifolia</i>	<i>eduardii</i>	<i>sideroxyla</i>
Catechin	6.61±0.73	177±7.09	85.3±10.5	82.3±4.00	16.4±1.65	35.7±2.21	130±5.83
Terminal units (%)	57	67	39	44	70	41	46
Extension units (%)	43	33	61	56	30	59	54
Gallocatechin	24.3±4.00	142±10.5	176±32.8	212±14.1	8.84±0.84	34.5±1.40	30.1±4.08
Terminal units (%)	21	48	34	54	100	26	22
Extension units (%)	79	53	66	46	0	74	78
Epicatechin gallate	-	9.66±0.61	4.52±0.63	3.20±0.48	-	0.25±0.02	2.58±0.33
Terminal units (%)	-	9	56	73	-	0	0
Extension units (%)	-	91	44	27	-	100	100
Epigallocatechin gallate	5.64±0.68	18.24±3.41	24.9±5.42	12.7±2.37	-	-	-
Terminal units (%)	-	0	40	0	-	-	-
Extension units (%)	100	100	60	100	-	-	-
Total procyanidins	36.5±4.27	347±18.5	291±44.1	310±18.6	25.3±0.82	70.5±3.53	163±6.81
mDP	3.92±0.63	1.80±0.10	2.77±0.33	2.00±0.06	1.25±0.08	2.94±0.24	2.42±0.01

Results were expressed as mean±standard deviation of three replicates

Table 4. Phenolic acids concentration (mg/L) present in seven herbal infusions of *Quercus* calculated in MRM mode using UPLC-QqQ

Phenolic acids	<i>grisea</i>	<i>resinosa</i>	<i>arizonica</i>	<i>convallata</i>	<i>durifolia</i>	<i>eduardii</i>	<i>sideroxyla</i>
Gallic acid	12.8±0.01	9.39±0.62	9.33±0.58	8.63±0.14	3.88±0.56	18.7±1.05	3.96±0.26
3,4-Dihydroxy benzoic acid	2.27±0.20	1.56±0.06	1.66±0.03	0.17±0.03	4.36±0.20	1.93±0.00	2.27±0.09
Chlorogenic acid	0.03±0.00	-	0.05±0.00	0.06±0.00	33.1±0.03	0.38±0.08	21.5±0.87
4-Hydroxybenzoic acid	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.08±0.00
4-O-Caffeoylquinic acid	-	-	-	0.002±0.00	-	0.01±0.00	0.02±0.00
Caffeic acid	0.15±0.00	0.09±0.00	0.02±0.00	-	-	-	-
Coumaric acid	3.26±0.14	0.10±0.00	0.23±0.09	-	-	2.43±0.09	-
Ferulic acid	0.04±0.00	-	0.01±0.00	-	-	-	-
Salicylic acid	-	-	0.04±0.00	0.02±0.00	0.08±0.00	-	0.04±0.00
Total phenolic acids	18.6±0.49	11.1±0.96	11.3±0.98	8.88±0.24	41.5±1.11	23.4±1.72	27.8±1.72

Results were expressed as mean±standard deviation of three replicates

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Table S1. Analytical parameters for the identification and quantification of phenolic acids in *Quercus* leave infusions by UPLC-QqQ.

Compound	Time (min)	m/z	MRM transitions (Collision energy)		Cone voltage	Linear range (ng)	Calibration curve	Correlation coefficient (r ²)
			Quantifier	Qualifier				
Galic acid	1.67	169	169>125 (16)	169> 79 (26)	44	6 - 30	1557.57±24.53	0.9989
3,4-Dihydroxybenzoic acid	3.20	153	153>109 (14)	153>81 (20)	20	3 - 30	480928±113.32	0.9963
Chlorogenic acid	4.47	353	353>191 (16)	353>135 (32)	52	6 - 30	26850.88±103.29	0.9971
4-Hydroxybenzoic acid	4.57	137	137>93 (12)	137>65 (26)	80	3 - 30	3678.61±139.05	0.9963
4-O-Caffeoylquinic acid	4.65	353	353>191 (22)	353>173 (18)	80	6 - 30	116696.16±750.94	0.9975
Caffeic acid	5.03	179	179>135 (16)	179>107 (20)	58	6 - 30	955.88±50.51	0.9943
Syringic acid	5.19	197	197>182 (14)	197>123 (22)	46	6 - 30	891.79±45.22	0.9931
2,4,6-Trihydroxybenzaldehyde	6.37	153	153>107 (14)	153>83 (22)	20	3 - 30	9781.61±821.56	0.9987
Coumaric acid	6.38	163	163>119 (16)	163> 93 (26)	36	6 - 30	2121.01±62.93	0.9975
Sinapic acid	6.69	223	223>164 (14)	223>149 (20)	36	6 - 30	1307.34±3.53	0.9957
Ferulic acid	6.75	193	193>178 (12)	193>134 (16)	60	6 - 30	1961.13±1.30	0.9989
4,5-Dicaffeoylquinic acid	7.19	515	515>353 (20)	515>179 (30)	14	2 - 20	47516.13±1532.79	0.9928
Rosmarinic acid	7.29	359	359>197 (16)	359> 161 (14)	40	6 - 30	7316.84±213.94	0.9966
3,4-Dicaffeoylquinic acid	7.75	515	515>353 (20)	515> 191 (20)	40	2 - 20	139017.57±1735.52	0.9985
Salicylic acid	7.93	137	137>93 (14)	137>65 (24)	40	6 - 30	6310.15±134.03	0.9981

Names in bold means phenolic compounds actually found in *Quercus* samples.

Figure S1. Qualitative comparison at 360 nm of the flavonoid profile of leaves, infusion and paste (solid residue) of *Quercus grisea*. Numbers correspond to compounds identified in Table 1.

